

The New Iraqi Journal Of Medicine

The Official Journal Of The Iraqi Ministry Of Health

Volume 4 Number 2 August 2008

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**The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine
The Official Peer Review Journal Of The
Iraqi Ministry of Health**

August 2008 Volume 4 Number 2

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Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) versus open biopsy in breast masses in Erbil

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Abstract

Background: Breast mass is one of the most common problems among females. Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) as a part of triple assessment has its important role in evaluation of breast masses to out the likelihood of breast cancer. The aim of this paper is to compare the results of FNAC and open biopsy in patients presented with palpable breast lump, and to determine the sensitivity and specificity of the FNAC of the breast lump.

Patients and method: 110 female patients (mean age 36.08; range 18-80 years), with breast lump were observed at Rizgary Teaching Hospital, Erbil. The patients were attending Rizgary teaching hospital and the (Center for early detection of breast cancer) in Maternity & Pediatric hospital during the period from July 2006 to July 2007. They underwent FNAC, and were then subjected to excisional biopsy to determine sensitivity and specificity of the FNAC. Both cytological and histopathology results were available for comparison.

Results: The cytological diagnosis was malignant in 5 cases (4.54%), suspicious in 20 cases (18.1%), benign in 85 cases (77.2%). Histological diagnosis of these 110 patients showed 87 cases (79%) with benign disease and 23 cases (21%) having malignant disease. The false negative values of FNAC were in 3 cases and the false positive values were in 1 case. Sensitivity of the FNAC was 57.1% with 98.7%

specificity, 80% positive predictive value and 96.4% negative predictive value, and the accuracy was 95.5%.

Conclusion: FNAC has low sensitivity (57.1%) and high specificity (98.7%). It is simple, cost effective and less traumatic method for diagnosis of the breast lump. It should be used as a routine method for determining the nature of the breast lumps, but it has a limited role in the management of breast cancer without the other elements of the triple test.

Introduction

FNAC is an accepted and established method to determine the nature of the lump and it may play an important role when it is difficult to determine the nature of breast lump by clinical examination. It has been shown that FNAC can reduce the number of open breast biopsies [1]. It establishes a diagnosis and management plan for the patient on the day of the clinic visit [2]. **The aim of this study is** to determine the sensitivity and specificity of FNAC and to compare the results of FNAC and open biopsy (OB) in patients presented with palpable breast lump.

Patients and methods

110 female patients (mean age 36.08; range 18-80 years), with breast lump were observed at Rizgary Teaching Hospital, Erbil. The patients were attending Rizgary teaching hospital and the (Center for early detection of breast cancer) in Maternity& Pediatric hospital during the period from July 2006 to July 2007 They underwent FNAC, and were then subjected to excisional biopsy to determine sensitivity and specificity of the FNAC. Both cytological and histopathology results were available for comparison.

Data were obtained from patients including: The name, age, marital state, parity, lactation, smoking, family history of BC, drug history, presence of pain, site of the mass. FNAC was performed for all patients by the histopathologists and some time by researcher, without using anesthesia, using sterile syringe with a needle of 22 gauge, after localization of the mass and disinfecting the area with absolute alcohol, fixing the lesion between the index fingers and the thumb, the mass were entered by the needle point, Aspiration is done by exerting gentle negative pressure through the syringe and maintaining negative pressure and moving the needle point within the lesion repeatedly forward & backward in different angles, then release the negative pressure before taking the needle out. All patients underwent open biopsy

under general anesthesia, and then the biopsy materials were sent in containers containing 10% formalin to the department of histopathology. The FNAC and OB results were recorded. The verbal consent were taken from all the enrolled patients, all of them informed about the purpose and the procedure of the study also the permission from the surgeons who were managing the

Patients that included in the study were taken. Statistically data were entered into a computer using the statistical package for social science (SPSS) version (15.0) and Microsoft Excel version. Statistical analysis was carried out using the standard tests, cross tabulations and Chi-square test. And the following measurements were obtained: sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value PPV, negative predictive value NPV, P value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

1. Age distributions: The peak incidence of breast mass was in the second decade of life. These as shown in figure (1).

Figure (1): Age distribution of patients

2. Age distribution of malignant cases: The peak incidence of malignant cases

Figure (2): Age distribution of malignant cases diagnosed by excisional biopsy

diagnosed in this study was in the fourth decade (40-49) as figure (2).

3. Marital state: Most of the cases in our study which were presented with breast mass were married 90.9%, only 9.1% were single as shown in figure (3).

Figure (3): Marital state among patient presented with breast mass.

4-FNAC and excisional biopsy results:

Out of 110 cases FNAC done in all of the cases, most of them were benign, 85 cases (77.3%), 5 cases (4.6%) were malignant and 20 cases (18.1%) were suspicious. The patients underwent OB, in which most of them were benign: 87cases (79%), 23cases were malignant (21%). P value of Chi-Square test in the difference between FNAC and OB was 0.00001, which is highly significant. As shown in table (1) and figure (4, 5).

Table (1): FNAC and excisional biopsy result

	Benign	Malignant	Total
Benign	82	3	85
Malignant	1	4	5
Suspicious	4	16	20
Total	87	23	110

Figure (4): FNAC report

Figure No (5): FNAC and EB result

5. Sensitivity and specificity of FNAC

figure -6: Of the 110, 20 were considered suspicious cases and were excluded. The results were obtained from 90 patients. Box (1): Definitions

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{\text{True Positive (TP)}}{\text{TP} + \text{False negative (FN)}} \times 100 = 57.1\%$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{\text{True negative cases (TN)}}{\text{TN}} = 98.7\%$$

$$\text{Positive predictive value} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{False negative (FP)}} \times 100 = 80\%$$

$$\text{Negative predictive value} = \frac{\text{TN}}{\text{TN} + \text{FN}} \times 10 = 96.4\%$$

$$\text{Total accuracy} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{Total No}} \times 100 = 95.5$$

Figure (6): Sensitivity and specificity of FNAC

Box (1): Definitions

Sensitivity Is the proportion of true positives (cases with positive screening tests) among all cases. $\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \times 100$

Specificity Is the proportion of true negatives (non cases with negative screening tests) among all non cases. $\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \times 100$

Predictive values is the denominators for these calculations are the number of persons with positive tests (TP+ FP) or negative tests (TN + FN).

Positive predictive value Is the proportion of true positives (cases with positive screening tests) among all those with positive tests. $\text{Positive predictive value} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \times 100$

Negative predictive value is the proportion of true negatives among all those with negative tests. $\text{Negative predictive value} = \frac{TN}{TN+FN} \times 100$

Total accuracy = $\frac{TP+TN}{\text{Total No}} \times 100$

FNAC for other reasons in association with breast mass

1. Presence of abnormal nipple discharge: Among our studied group 15 cases (13.63%) of them having abnormal nipple discharge in association with breast mass , FNAC results revealed that the percentage of malignant cases were more among cases with no nipple discharge (Figure-7). P value association between cases with abnormal nipple discharge and FNAC results by Chi-square test were 0.5 which is not significant.

Figure (7): FNAC result and presence of abnormal nipple discharge

2. Presence of enlarged axillary lymph node: 3 cases (2.72%) out of 110 cases had enlarged axillary LN; in association with BM in whom FNAC were done, in which 20% were suspicious and 10% were malignant Figure -8. P value of association of FNAC results and presence of enlarged axillary LN by chi-square test were 0.002, which is significant.

Figure (8): FNAC result in cases with enlarged axillary LN.

3. Positive family history of breast cancer: Among the malignant cases which diagnosed by FNAC 80% of them had no family history of breast cancer. Figure-9 P value by Chi-square test in association between the result of FNAC and family history of malignancy was 0.1. That is not significant.

Figure (9): malignant cases among patients with positive family HX of breast cancer

4. Breast cancer and lactation: Out of 23 malignant cases, 16 cases (69.56%) were not lactating and 7 cases (30.44%) were lactating.

5. Drugs taken by the patients: Out of 110 cases, 65 patients had no HX .of chronic

drug taking, while 39 patients had history of taking contraceptive pills. As in table -2

Table (2): Drugs taken by the patients

Drugs	No. of patients
No drugs.	65
Contraceptive pills	39
Hormone replacement.(progesterone, bromocriptin)	3
Other drugs like (anti hypertensive, oral hypoglycemic drug)	3
Total.	110

Discussion

The FNAC result in this study, 77.2% were benign, 18.1% were suspicious for malignancy and 4.54% were malignant, while the result in OB 79% were benign, 21% were malignant. The higher percentage of OB result than that of FNAC was related to the false negative result which was detected in the study and the number of suspicious cases. This result was of quite agreement to that of Aziz et al [3], in a study done Pakistan [3]. Lower percentage of malignant cases were found in (Chieduzi et al. [4] 2003), in a study done in Saudi Arabia (KSA) respectively. P value of different between FNAC and Open biopsy was 0.0001, which is highly significant. This means that in our locality we can not depend on FNAC alone for diagnosis of breast cancer without excisional biopsy because we have many suspicious cases that diagnosed by FNAC which were not conclusive and for that reason we have low sensitive FNAC in this study. The false negative result was 2.7

%; the false positive result was 0.9 %. The sensitivity of FNAC was 57.1% with high specificity 98.7%. and the PPV & NPV was 80, 96.4 respectively. The low false +ve positive result of FNAC in this study is compatible to that of (Dennison et al., UK [5], Aziz et al [3], and Hea et al. [6] in China). In comparison to El Tahir et al. [3], in Aberdeen Royal hospital they had higher percentage of false positive result (10.7%) which they blame inadequate sample and inexperienced pathologist. On the other hand (Yu et al [7]. 1997; Chaiwun [8], Dennison et al [4]; Sauer et al [9]. 2 Aziz et al. [3], .They had higher percentage of FNAC result especially in malignant cases. Their results were 4.4%, 7.2%, 6%, 8.2% & 14.7% respectively. Regarding the sensitivity the result in this study was in good agreement with those obtained by (Agerwal et al. [10] Britton [11], Chew [12], and Sinnatambay [13]. Higher sensitivity of FNAC in comparison to this study, were detected by El Tahir [2]. Their results were 90 %, 88.7, and 93.1 respectively. Which is related to the higher percentage of positive results which diagnosed by FNAC in their study. Very high specificity of FNAC in our study were compatible to that of (Yu et al[7]., 1997; El Tahir et al[2]., Aziz et al., Hea et al[6]., 2007). Lower specificity were detected in a study done in Saudi Arabia; Chew et al.[12]. Their results were 81.8%, 63.3% respectively, because of higher percentage of false positive results. FNAC were done in cases with abnormal nipple discharge which was found in 13.63% of cases. This is in agreement with that of (Santen and Mansel, [12] which they stated that the presence of a discharge in association with a palpable mass and positive result on mammography or ultrasonography warrants evaluation of the mass and the likelihood of cancer is increased. In this study FNAC of patients with change in the size of breast revealed that 75% were benign, 25% were malignant.

P value association of the FNAC result and change in the breast size were highly significant, this is in agreement with that of (Harvey et al., [14]). Regarding the family history of BC. This study showed that among the malignant cases that diagnosed by FNAC 80% of them had no family history of breast cancer & p value association between the result of FNAC & family history of breast cancer was not significant (0.1). Because we had many malignant results that missed in this study by FNAC which reported as suspicious. This is in contrast to that of (Armstrong et al. [15], 2000) they stated that the risk of BC increased in cases of positive family history even when they are negative for BRCA mutation gene. Among 39 patients who were on contraceptive pills 33.3% of them were malignant, while the remaining 76.7% were benign. Devlin [16] suggests a link between high-dose combined oral contraceptives that were discontinued in most countries years ago and an increased risk of BC among women with a strong family history of the disease.

Conclusions

FNAC has high specificity and low sensitivity in diagnosis of breast cancer, because in many cases FNA gave only a suspicious diagnosis (not decisive). Core needle biopsy is recommended in suspicious cases, because it can give a definitive diagnosis of malignancy, as well as the grade of the tumor. Moreover, it can differentiate between in situ carcinoma and infiltrative carcinoma. Immunocytochemistry and molecular genetic techniques are recommended to be done in suspicious cases to reach the diagnosis and to increase the sensitivity of FNAC. Frozen section and if not available an open biopsy should be done in suspicious cases to reach the diagnosis

when immunocytochemistry and CNB were non conclusive or not available.

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